

Newsletter EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

25 November 2025, Edition 13

Questions to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (Q2E)

All Q2E answers are available [online](#).

- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-002](#): Culling Individuals
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-004](#): Broiler Cannibalism Causative Factors
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-005](#): Pre-stun shocks in waterbath stunning of Poultry (ongoing)
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-006](#): Broiler Cannibalism Prevention
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-007](#): Broiler Cannibalism Emergency Measures (ongoing)
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-008](#): Duck catching (ongoing)

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→ The Q2E webform is available online [here](https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/QuerywebformIQ3/questionnaire.htm) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/QuerywebformIQ3/questionnaire.htm>

→ You can download [here](#) the webform in PDF to prepare your Q2E submission.

Meeting the EU Member States Competent Authorities

The **sixth EU-network meeting** between representatives of Competent Authorities and the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, with the participation of one DG SANTE unit G5 representative, one EFSA representative and two EFTA representatives as observers, took place physically at Anses headquarters in Maisons-Alfort, France in October 2025, 01-02, during 2*0.5 days.

In total 35 participants, from **17 EU Member States (MSs)** participated, including **22 delegates from EU MSs**.

Participants took the opportunity to network during the ice breakers and social activities (visit of the Fragonard Museum followed by a join dinner) and exchange on various subject during the World Café and the “Eat & meet” sessions. Four participants took the opportunity to present/discuss their topics of interest during the plenary session.

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Link to the presentations pdf: [link](#)

2025 Highlights

★ Four EURCAWs meeting with EU Animal Welfare NRCs and SBs

On **15 October 2025**, the four EURCAWs organised an online meeting for the **National Reference Centres (NRCs) for Animal Welfare and the National Supporting Bodies (SBs)** of Competent Authorities. A total of 41 people attended the meeting. Excluding EURCAW and DG SANTE members, **23 participants from 14 EU MSs** were present. The meeting aimed to facilitate mutual updates between the NRCs/SBs and the four EURCAWs, as well as promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange.

The topics discussed and the presentations can be found in the meeting report [here](#).

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📺 Webishop on Depopulation methods in cases of Avian Influenza

The Webishop on **Depopulation methods in cases of Avian Influenza** has been organized on **November 6th, 2025**. The online event focused on the activity conducted by the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA on the depopulation methods used in the European Union during avian influenza outbreaks.

It was structured in two parts:

- 1) **A webinar** in which EURCAW-Poultry-SFA presented the key deliverables of the depopulation activity, namely an overview of the main depopulation methods used in the European Union and their ranking based on poultry welfare – following the principles of the selection guide developed to help competent authorities choose the most appropriate depopulation method according to the specific context at stake.
- 2) **An interactive workshop** during which participants reviewed the welfare assessment protocols developed by EURCAW-Poultry-SFA for on-site depopulation operations when non-penetrative captive bolt stunning, whole-house gassing or gassing in gradually-filled containers are used. Participants provided feedback on their validity and feasibility in field conditions.

A total of **103 participants from 15 EU MSs** participated.

The event aimed to help participants understand which depopulation methods should be applied from a welfare perspective depending on the specific context encountered (e.g., depending on the flock size, species at stake, or the available human and technical resources). It also aimed to gather feedback from field actors on the validity and feasibility of the welfare-assessment protocols developed, to ensure that they are usable in practice and applicable across countries despite variations in operating procedures.

The webinar presentation is available [here](#).

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